

Methodology of forming the skill of using educational dictionaries in elementary grades

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Abstract: This article analyzes the scientific and theoretical basis of using dictionaries in primary education.

Keywords: Uzbek language, vocabulary, mother tongue education, importance, spelling, improving literacy, increasing vocabulary, important resource, student's main advisor, etc. One of the main tasks of primary education is the formation of general learning skills and competencies in students. Among the general learning skills, the ability to use various dictionaries and reference books takes an important place. At the moment, the need and habit of a person to understand his linguistic difficulties and try to solve them with the help of a dictionary is a personal characteristic of a person, one of the signs of his culture. Thus, dictionaries can be considered not only for teaching the student, but also as a means of education.

Currently, many dictionaries with different functions have been published and are being published in our country. For example, a high school student can use not only a spelling dictionary, but also explanatory dictionaries, word formation dictionaries, borrowed words, obsolete words, synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, etc. But does the student turn to the dictionary knowingly?! According to our observation, most students do not use the resources they have, even if they have the dictionaries they need on the bookshelf. One of the reasons for such a phenomenon is embodied in the following well-known sentence: everything begins with childhood. If the child does not develop the need to refer to dictionaries at the initial stages of education, if he does not develop the skills of finding the right information quickly and aiming at the aids, he will not be a full user of the available vocabulary. suspicion of becoming a person. That is why it is already clear that it is necessary to start working with dictionaries from the first grades.

When it is customary for a primary school student to turn to a dictionary (in a problem-related manner), he puts linguistic problems before himself, is ready to consciously find answers to them, and is ready to do this. it can be considered that the basis for educating a cultured person who can do Today, a primary school student

has a large number of dictionaries. In the near future, working with a dictionary in a native language class should be a regular activity in any class, and working with different types of dictionaries should become a necessity. Working with the dictionary should be included in every lesson: explaining the meaning of a word, writing the word correctly, pronouncing it correctly, explaining its structure (making). All words are written on the board in advance. Children's opinion is compared with the correct option in the dictionary. In this place, children are also given homework: the meaning of the word from the dictionary (explanatory dictionary), correct spelling (spelling dictionary), correct pronunciation (orthographic dictionary), to determine the meaning of any phrase (phraseological dictionary), etc. In the next lesson, the assignment will be checked and a new assignment will be given. In this way, the skills of working with a dictionary are formed in students, and then their competence. In each lesson, it is possible to recommend students to complete an individual task for working with the dictionary: to prepare a dictionary dictation on the previous topic, and to perform the role of a teacher in the next lesson. This type of work will undoubtedly arouse interest in children.

All this requires the teacher to methodically prepare for the development of the skills of using linguistic dictionaries in young students. For this system, first of all, it is necessary to determine the series of skills, which are the structural works (operations) of the complex skill of using the dictionary. Basic vocabulary skills include: 1. Using auxiliary dictionaries for textbooks. 2. Carefully read the text of the introductory article. 3. To determine the language unit that is described according to the name of the dictionary. 4. Working with the alphabetic word index. 5. Make and remember the vocabulary structure plan. 6. Make and keep in mind the plan of the dictionary article. 7. Work with conventional signs, symbols, conventional abbreviations. 8. Use read-review and read-search when working with dictionaries. Elementary school students should know (determine) the following: 1. The name of the dictionary. 2. The author and editor of the dictionary. 3. Publisher and year of publication. 4. The type of dictionary. 5. The function of the dictionary. 6. The arrangement of words in the dictionary: alphabetically, cellularly, thematically. To make the work easier, it is recommended to make a bookmark-note in each dictionary with conventional signs and abbreviations. As a result of studying the experience of teachers, it can be concluded that vocabulary work should take the leading place in the lessons of the mother tongue. The effectiveness of this work

depends on the professional skills of the teacher. Use of new technologies increases children's interest in lessons. And working with a dictionary - one of the new technologies in teaching the mother tongue - is a culture cultivation technology. Students should be able to use all types of vocabulary. This undoubtedly increases their cultural and speech level.

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